

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Stevens****FIRST NAME: Kirsten****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access) Plagiarism rate: 7%

The author used the following software: Word for Mac Version 16.54

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text:

1. Essay Writing Basics (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-11)
3. Writing Guidelines (EUCLID 2021, 13-15)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 16-26)
5. Usage of American Versus British English (EUCLID 2021, 26-35)
6. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2021, 55-60)
7. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2021, 53-65)

EFFECTIVE WRITING AS AN ELEMENT OF DOCTORAL EDUCATION

1) INTRODUCTION

I have held several leadership roles over the past twenty-five years, including the ownership and management of my own company. In each position, I wrote formal and informal documents for both internal and external communications. These documents ranged from daily emails and team memos to vendor contracts and Requests for Proposals (RFPs). Though I attended university in the United States, while living in The Bahamas I was exposed to the British style of writing. Over time, I developed a writing style that incorporates elements from both American and British writing. One issue that I struggle with and believe to be quite common is the distraction of reading and interpreting poorly written documents. It is difficult to critique content and develop responses to unprofessional material. Therefore, it is vital to establish a foundation for solid writing habits. The course, ACA-401D, aims to achieve this through its extensive review of essay writing basics, style guides, and potential writing pitfalls. The value of this process cannot be overstated. "Writing is the vehicle that most graduate programs embrace as the means for reviewing how well students are able to assimilate knowledge and integrate that knowledge into new ideas" (Ondrusek 2012, 179).

Thus, the first assignment of ACA-401D is a helpful reminder of the guidelines for professional writing that form the basis of doctoral academic writing.

2) ESSAY WRITING BASICS

The course begins with a summary of the essential components of essay writing. “An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2021, 1). To persuade readers, the essay must answer a question and should provide supporting data for the argument. Presenting relevant examples and factual evidence will enable the reader to understand the author’s perspective and consider the validity of the theory being discussed.

As with all well-executed projects, an essay always begins with a plan. This is an opportunity for the author to organize their thoughts, develop the strategy for the delivery of the concept, and assess the full extent of their knowledge of the topic. Planning includes scheduling the work to be done, researching the topic, organizing the ideas, writing the first draft, and having a friend or colleague critique the work. I find it disappointing in my field of work that much of the professional writing being done is not planned out in advance. Ideas are not fully formulated, and these are not conveyed.

Additionally, the material is often redundant or duplicative, and critical points are not emphasized or supported. These are missed opportunities. We live in a time when our written word is easily accessed via numerous digital mediums, and our ability to share information that can impact others is very high. I believe we have a responsibility to deliver our messages effectively, accurately, and clearly. Sloppy work, providing misinformation, and allowing for ambiguity can confuse and diminish the author’s ability to convince the reader.

The research portion of the planning process enables the author to supplement existing knowledge with readings that provide relevant content on the topic. “A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers” (EUCLID 2021, 2). To stay organized, it is helpful to conduct a full review of all of the material identified. The writer should make notes and identify sources for later use in referencing.

It may not seem important, but the first draft of an essay is crucial in writing. A first draft is an opportunity to write everything about the particular topic and then re-organize the information, discard irrelevant ideas and refine the writing itself. Many well-recognized authors utilize the first draft process. Incorporating an introduction, body, and conclusion into the draft ensures that the reader will grasp the flow of the information. It can also be very helpful in testing out the argument that underpins the essay. I have often found gaping holes in my work as a result of structuring it into this format. It has helped me identify opportunities to enhance my research and add supporting evidence.

3) PLAGIARISM

Students must fully understand and acknowledge the concept of plagiarism as their writing style and habits will form the basis of their future work. It is not unusual for students to procrastinate and feel very pressured to complete projects in a timely fashion. This can lead to plagiarism. In the professional world, it is pervasive to see the work of individuals not appropriately recognized in presentations, papers, teaching materials, and professional training. It could be argued that a good deal of these materials contains information that is relatively commonplace and can be found in various sources. However, where the interpretation of facts by an individual leads to a unique solution, process, or system created by an individual, there is no doubt that the originator of the information is entitled to recognition for their work. I have seen several instances whereby writers or content creators have assumed authorship for material that was not theirs and have been able to reap significant financial benefits from the repurposing of content.

The most effective method of preventing plagiarism is to educate students to understand the importance of producing their work and crediting authorship as appropriate. They are then empowered to take full responsibility for their work and their education as a whole. Discipline is an effective method of addressing plagiarism. Still, first, we must drive home the concept that plagiarizing is a severe offense that can significantly limit one's tendency to think creatively. When the responsibility of crafting unique and meaningful work is removed, we become lazy and dependent. Ultimately, ensuring that students do not plagiarize also opens doors for them to stretch their thinking, test the boundaries of their knowledge and take risks in their writing.

4) WRITING GUIDELINES

The ACA-401D writing guidelines are intended to provide a review of the basic principles that guide academic writing. I find it particularly helpful to remember staying focused and writing clearly (EUCLID 2021, 14). I know I am not unique in that I tend to fall into the trap of wandering down confusing lines of thought when working on a piece of writing. Suppose I am fortunate enough to realize what I am doing and take a step back. In that case, I typically see that I have drifted away from the essay's thesis and am attempting to make connections that are not supported by evidence or are simply too flimsy to illustrate a point. I also tend to include as much information as possible rather than selectively include the most relevant and compelling facts. Embellishing for the sake of creating an overly dramatic effect is also a habit that I have noticed occasionally in my work. Ideally, "your writing should focus readers' attention on the ideas you wish to express, not on the words you have chosen to express those ideas" (EUCLID 2021, 15).

Taking the views being discussed seriously is another area I believe I can continue developing. It is in our nature to have strong feelings about what we write or research. Taking the time to understand that other writers have done their homework, questioned their arguments, and incorporated responses from others (EUCLID 2021, 15) helps us think with maturity and curiosity. Dismissing other people's work at face value, and worse,

developing strong objections to others' views is a simple and amateur mistake that can limit our capacity to explore our thinking.

5) STYLE GUIDE

Using a style guide in writing ensures consistency and allows for more than one author to contribute without influencing that work with their own personal writing style. It makes sense that each author should research writing styles and, if they have not been directed to a particular style guide, identify one for their writing. I have adopted some characteristics in my writing that came about organically, either due to a reference I came across, influence from colleagues, or living in another country. However, I have never consciously decided which style I would use. I recognize now that this inconsistency can be annoying and distracting to the reader.

As suggested, I looked up the BBC News style guide and am interested in the extensive coverage of potential style usage. I can see that a news agency would find it necessary to expound on their style guidelines to this degree and with such detail, considering the influence their reporting can have and the need for legal considerations when reporting facts. Another item of note is that the website lists tautologies and the most common ones that the organization recommends avoiding such as “advance warning,” “armed gunmen” and “universal panacea.”

6) USAGE OF AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

As mentioned, I have lived in several countries where British English is used. As a teenager, I attended boarding school in England and later lived in the Turks and Caicos Islands and The Bahamas. In those countries, the pronunciation and spelling of words was different from the style used in the American schools I attended in Guatemala, Costa Rica, and Mexico. What is clear to me is that while both British and American English are correct, the writer must adopt and commit to one style to reduce confusion and distraction. Upon my return to the United States, I struggled with the use of punctuation in a formal letter addressing a wife and husband, as in “Mr. and Mrs. Smith.” The British version of this is “Mr and Mrs Smith”, which can appear strange to an American.

Other distinctions include words with a different spelling but the same pronunciation, such as “plough” and “plow,” “cheque” and “check,” “gaol” and “jail,” and “manoeuvre” and “maneuver” (EUCLID 2021, 27). These differences are obvious in written communications; however, other usage differences are more likely to be detected in the spoken word such as words with a different pronunciation but same spelling, including “leisure,” “controversy,” “dynasty,” and “schedule” (EUCLID 2021, 26). I know that many of my American counterparts enjoy hearing the pronunciation of these words almost as much as we enjoy hearing a different accent.

7) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

When I was a student in boarding school in England, my friend and roommate, Sarah, was preparing for her Latin A-level exam. I was intrigued by her study of the language but was unsure of the value of its application in modern-day conversation. Today, Latin is still taught in some schools, and we have incorporated many Latin words, roots of words, abbreviations, and expressions in the English language. From the more common such as A.M., meaning ‘before noon,’ to lesser-known abbreviations, such as Q.E.D., meaning ‘which was to be shown,’ our oral and written daily communications include many Latin abbreviations and expressions.

The use of Latin expressions and abbreviations crosses into many different personal and professional areas of our lives. In my work as a consultant to nonprofits, I often explain that a particular board seat is “ex officio” (out of one’s duty or office) or that my service for a specific project is “pro bono” (for the public good, at no cost). A donor may make a “bona fide” (in good faith) pledge of funds to a nonprofit with a “caveat” (caution/warning) that the funds be used for a specific purpose (EUCLID 2021, 59). In my role as advisor, I try to ensure that the group I’m working with is clear on the meaning of the expressions since the language in board documents and minutes is typically passed on to successive board members. For example, confusion can arise when board members are “ex officio” as there is a general misunderstanding about these board members’ roles, responsibilities, and even voting rights. The term refers to the fact that “ex officio” board members are assigned a seat on a board because of another position they hold. Any further specifics regarding their board seat are not inherent to that term and should be clarified in the organization’s bylaws.

8) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE

I have worked in several industry sectors, including hospitality, healthcare, retail, nonprofit management, and executive search. I have led teams, recruited staff members, and contracted with vendors in every sector. These managerial activities require me to review documents, prepare contracts, vet resumes and examine biographies. Documents that are presented with grammatical and style errors tend to make their way almost immediately to piles classified either “do not consider” or “return for revisions.” I am certain that there have been numerous highly qualified candidates whose résumé has crossed my desk who have been disqualified due to poor writing.

Similarly, I am convinced that exceptional writing and adherence to appropriate style guidelines have favorably supported RFPs that I have submitted. “What really counts is your ability to develop a piece of writing into an effective finished product” (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999, 3). A writer’s finished product includes all of the elements of style, and for this discussion, Chicago style.

There are particular areas of Chicago style provided in the ACA-401D coursepack that tend to be more generally troublesome for writers than others. One of those is the use

of compound words. These are “two or more words that work together in a specified order” (EUCLID 2021, 45). We often see writers creating their own compound words or inappropriately hyphenating certain compound words. Compound words are either full-time or conditional; the former are always hyphenated, whereas the latter are only hyphenated as adjectives. This distinction in conditional compounds is important because the meaning of words or phrases can be significantly distorted with the misuse of hyphenation.

Another area that writers often struggle with is quotations, which must be placed in quotation marks or indented as a block quote (EUCLID 2021, 47) and must include a referral to the source document. While it is critical to quote accurately from the works of others, there are some areas where it is permissible to adjust. For example, if the clarity of a phrase can be enhanced by adding words, this can be done by using brackets. Italics may be used to add emphasis but must be clearly indicated either immediately after the change or adding them to the end of a quote. It is permissible to quote in a foreign language, however the words quoted must be reproduced exactly as they would be in the original language. Additionally, Chicago style now permits the use of quotes that include a citation from another source without citing it. When it comes to errors, it “may be appropriate to emphasize the original is being quoted faithfully” (EUCLID 2021, 47). This is done by adding the Latin term *sic* in italics or underlined.

Whether writers are just starting or are seasoned writers, it is the awareness of style elements that matters most. It is unrealistic to expect writers to memorize all of the style guidelines; it is more vital for them to know where to find the guidelines and adopting a willingness to critique their own work.

9) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401D coursepack study materials and accompanying videos are an excellent basis for every doctoral student who is getting started with their academic writing. The coursepack can be printed and used as a reference guide and the many examples given help to clarify the writing usage guides.

To clearly convey a message, present a convincing argument, demonstrate compelling findings, or simply provide thoughtful observations, material must be presented in a way that is easy for the reader to consume. As doctoral students, my peers and I are tasked with not only absorbing and processing concepts related to our program, but also with presenting our own interpretation and research in a sophisticated, professional, and ethical manner. I look forward to continuing to develop my writing skills and learn the methodology behind scholarly writing. There is a degree of humility required to embark on the first course of a program that is focused entirely on writing guidelines. Deep down, I believe we all feel we are already excellent writers, and the first exercise of this course has forced me to take a step back and do a bit of self-analysis. I have never learned how to properly cite my sources and have never used Grammarly, and I recognize that I have much to learn. These skills will be helpful for the rest of my academic and professional career.

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